

HOW AI AND MOBILE APPS CAN ENHANCE STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCIES

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Abstract. *The transformative potential of artificial intelligence (AI) and mobile applications in improving students' communicative competencies, particularly in the context of English language learning is addressed in this study. Moreover, the study focuses on how technology may be integrated into educational settings and shows how gamification and AI-driven tools and mobile applications can support individualized learning, provide real-time feedback, and increase learner engagement. These tools adjust to each learner's unique needs by utilizing adaptive algorithms, which makes language education more efficient and engaging. A literature review method used for this research analyzes the effects of artificial intelligence technologies on enhancing linguistic, sociolinguistic, and strategic competencies by examining various studies, including speech recognition systems, chatbots, and language exchange platforms. On the one hand, the findings demonstrate that artificial intelligence systems foster intercultural awareness through engagement with native speakers and improve pronunciation and grammar through real-time feedback. On the other hand, mobile apps with gamified elements keep users interested, encouraging continuous practice and group learning.*

Furthermore, this study emphasizes how important artificial intelligence and mobile apps are in bridging the gap between abstract concepts and practical communication. In particular, AI-based tools provide learners with constant opportunities to practice real-life scenarios, improving both fluency and accuracy. These platforms also offer learners access to a variety of cultural and linguistic contexts, making language acquisition more immersive and authentic. Flexible, inclusive, and culturally competent are only a few of the many benefits that modern technologies bring. However, several issues such as digital equity and an excessive dependence on technology are also covered in this work. In conclusion, the study recommends professional development for teachers and more research into the long-term effects to support the deliberate integration of artificial intelligence and mobile technology into language education.

Keywords: *communicative competence, artificial intelligence in language learning, mobile applications in education, AI-driven language tools, real-time feedback, gamification, language exchange platforms, intercultural competence, sociolinguistic competence.*

INTRODUCTION

Technology integration in education has significantly reshaped traditional teaching methods in recent years. Specifically, mobile apps and artificial intelligence (AI) have emerged as key tools for improving students' communication skills. Communicative competence defined by M.Canale and M.Swain [Canale & Swain, 1980; 6], encompasses linguistic, sociolinguistic, discourse, and strategic abilities. This paper explores how students' communicative competencies can be enhanced and language acquisition facilitated by AI-driven tools and mobile applications, especially when learning English as a second language (ESL). The ability to communicate effectively in English is not just a language requirement in today's increasingly interconnected world, but it is also a crucial instrument for international business, cross-cultural exchange, and

international cooperation. Education systems are under more pressure than ever to guarantee that students can communicate effectively in a second language, especially English, as a result of the shift towards global integration. Efficient communication is important for interpersonal relationships in this context, and teachers are using mobile apps and artificial intelligence in growing numbers to improve language learning as technology advances. The implications for language instruction as well as how these tools can influence students' communicative competencies are discussed in this study.

As mentioned above, the communicative competence model developed by M.Canale and M.Swain [Canale & Swain, 1980; 6] provides the framework for this research. The model places a strong emphasis on the value of both grammatical knowledge and contextual language usage skills. In the context of language learning, communicative competence ensures that learners not only understand the grammar rules but also use the language effectively in social interactions, making it an important aspect of modern teaching methods. In light of this, recent studies highlight how technology can improve these aspects of communication [Chapelle, 2019; 577]. Through various platforms, mobile applications and artificial intelligence tools have been proven in numerous studies to facilitate language learning. For instance, gamification features in applications such as Duolingo enhance student interest by making language learning engaging and accessible [Ghafar et al., 2023; 26]. According to J.Hamari et al. [Hamari, 2014; 3025], mobile applications are important as well since they use gamification techniques to draw students in with interactive tasks. Similarly, artificial intelligence tools like chatbots further contribute to communicative competence by enabling conversational practice in a safe, simulated environment [Kukulka-Hulme, 2021; 124]. It is impossible to overstate how important artificial intelligence is in helping students practice having spontaneous conversations since it allows them to participate in conversations that are designed to resemble actual situations in which language is used. Moreover, real-time feedback mechanisms in applications such as Spechache offer immediate correction for grammar and pronunciation, which significantly accelerates learners' progress as stated in A.P. Harahap and A.A. Dalimunthe [Harahap & Dalimunthe, 2024; 1069]. Furthermore, language exchange platforms enhance sociolinguistic competence by facilitating real engagement with native speakers. As stated by M.Roussou [Roussou, 2006; 69], the integration of virtual reality and augmented reality technology presents a bright prospect for immersive language learning, enabling learners to participate in authentic conversations.

AI-driven conversational models, such as ChatGPT, are increasingly recognized as revolutionary tools for language learning. W.R.A. Bin-Hady et al. [Bin-Hady et al., 2023; 2] emphasized that the ChatGPT is a great tool for English Language Teaching (ELT) because it can customize interactions to the needs of the learners, simulate real-world conversational situations, and offer prompt feedback grounded in sound pedagogical principles. These technologies, which blend accessibility with adaptability, promise to revolutionize language acquisition by offering customized learning experiences grounded in real-world scenarios.

The increasing use of artificial intelligence in language acquisition has sparked concerns regarding the direction of pedagogy and whether or not artificial intelligence can replace or supplement traditional classroom environments. However, the teacher's position as a facilitator is still important for the social and emotional aspects of learning, which are more difficult for artificial intelligence to reproduce, even though it can offer personalized learning experiences.

Building on the insights from these studies, it is evident that the integration of artificial intelligence technologies, including chatbots, mobile applications, and conversational models like ChatGPT, plays a pivotal role in enhancing language learners' communicative competence. The following sections explore how artificial intelligence and mobile apps specifically contribute to the development of the above-mentioned skills, providing a deeper analysis of their unique advantages over traditional learning methods.

Before delving into the role of artificial intelligence and mobile applications in language learning and teaching, it is essential to first explore the foundational concepts of communication skills and communicative competence. A general definition of "communication" is the process of information being sent from one person to another by verbal and nonverbal means [Iksan et al., 2012; 72]. The most common form of communication is verbal, two-way, and involves providing feedback on the message received. It also uses a particular language. The sharing of information, viewpoints, and ideas with a defined goal is another aspect of communication. In addition to spoken exchanges, information can also be shared by signs or symbols. Another definition of communication is the simultaneous sharing and providing of meaning through symbolic interactions [Seiler & Beall, 2005; 25]. It has been suggested that communication begins when a message or piece of information is transmitted via a device or channel from the sender (speaker, writer) to the receiver (listener, reader), and then the recipient responds by deciphering and interpreting the information. According to these definitions, information providers, recipients, and feedback are all considered components of communication, and knowledge is developed through the repetition of these activities.

"Communicative competence" was first described by American linguist Avram Noam Chomsky as the ability of an ideal emitter or receiver to produce or comprehend an unlimited number of grammatically accurate phrases through their research in the field of generative linguistics [Lesenciuc & Nagy, 2009; 37]. N.Chomsky thus concentrated on the semantic/syntactic projection of communication rather than taking into consideration the pragmatic aspect of it. As a consequence, they created the term "linguistic competence", [Chomsky, 2006; 4] which refers to "the way language is used or acquired" and is predicated on the principle of universal grammar. In simpler terms, the syntactic dimension of Chomskyan linguistic competence can be defined as an ideal speaker's capacity to use an abstract system of speech rules once they have mastered the semantic dimension, which deals with the link between signs and the objects they represent. The term "communicative competence" has changed in the field of linguistics and communication, particularly concerning its applicability to a flexible reference frame, due to the research conducted by American linguist and anthropologist Dell Hymes. According to this interpretation, "competence" refers to the knowledge people require in order to successfully communicate and engage with others, as well as their capacity to adjust to various communicative contexts [Hymes, 1972; 269]. As per D.Hymes' belief that communication cannot be studied in isolation but rather must be viewed in the context of the impact it has on individuals' thoughts, communication competence cannot be reduced to a formulation that only takes into account the syntactic and semantic components. As stated by D.Hymes [Hymes, 1972; 269], we must view communication as the application of a few particular competencies in real-world situations. From N. Chomsky's standpoint, he takes a different theoretical approach, focusing on language knowledge and grammatically correct communication. Building on D.Hymes' theory, M.Canale and M.Swain integrate linguistic competence into the broader notion of communicative competence, contending

that certain language usage rules are meaningless in the absence of grammatical norms. Beginning with a critique of D.Hymes, M.Canale, and M.Swain first present a communicative competence that is centered on the grammatical, sociolinguistic, and strategic dimensions. Later, they also include the socio-cultural and discursive competencies, which are components of sociolinguistic competence. Grammatical competence includes understanding of vocabulary, structure, word creation, pronunciation, spelling, and sentence construction. Understanding sociolinguistic norms for language use, or the ability to use the language in a variety of sociolinguistic contexts, communicate within the parameters set by a specific topic of discussion, or use appropriate grammar forms for various communicative functions, are all components of sociolinguistic competence. Discursive competence is the ability to comprehend and produce writings that meet the general standards of discourse, which are coherence, relevance, and pertinence. Lastly, strategic competence involves the strategies employed to overcome potential communicative challenges, ensuring effective interaction.

In conclusion, successful interaction in a variety of circumstances depends on the relationship between communicative competence and communication skills. Comprehending the complex aspects of communication, both its theoretical foundations and real-world applications, helps people navigate social relationships more effectively. Through the incorporation of grammatical, sociolinguistic, and strategic elements, communicative competence provides people with the means to modify their communication approaches for a variety of audiences and situations. A thorough comprehension of these ideas will be necessary for efficient communication in a world where communication is becoming more and more intertwined as language continues to change.

Numerous studies have demonstrated the potential of artificial intelligence and mobile applications to enhance students' communicative competence in the English language learning process. As O.Komar [Komar, 2022; 138] discussed in their research, mobile applications and artificial intelligence tools can facilitate the development of communication skills and provide advantages including simplified classroom integration and enhanced test scores. Utilizing adaptive learning technology, mobile apps such as Babbel [Kessler et al., 2023; 2] and Memrise [Abarghoui & Taki, 2018; 1758] provide activities that get harder as students get better, keeping students challenged but not overwhelmed. This flexibility is essential for maintaining students' interest in the subject matter and encouraging ongoing development. Artificial intelligence technologies offer continuous oral practice opportunities and individualized feedback, according to individual needs, and promote more effective learning. These technologies include speech recognition systems and voice assistants. In speaking examinations, experimental research shows that learners who use ICT and AI tools score better than those who learn through conventional means as claimed by E.Madhavi et al. [Madhavi et al., 2023; 144]. The benefits of artificial intelligence in education merit additional investigation in order to better prepare students for successful English communication, even in the face of obstacles like data privacy and overreliance [Busso & Sanchez, 2024; 9-10]. By offering individualized learning experiences, artificial intelligence has completely changed the way people learn languages. Sophisticated algorithms are employed by platforms like Duolingo to evaluate students' strengths and shortcomings, enabling personalized lessons that address individual needs [Ghafar et al., 2023; 26]. When students interact with material that is appropriate for their present ability levels, personalization results in more effective learning outcomes.

Moreover, artificial intelligence systems offer real-time feedback, a critical component of effective language learning. For instance, programs such as Speechace not only provide immediate correction for grammar and pronunciation but also allow students to monitor their progress over time, leading to more rapid progress [Harahap & Dalimunthe, 2024; 1069]. In conjunction with tools like Duolingo, which gamifies the learning process, students experience a dynamic and interactive learning environment that reinforces both accuracy and engagement. Since students sometimes advance at different speeds in language study, this flexibility is especially valuable. Furthermore, the usefulness of artificial intelligence technologies in enhancing students' oral communication skills has been shown in several studies. As an instance, an investigation carried out at VFSTR University in India found that AI-based mobile applications greatly improved the fluency and accuracy of technical students' oral communication skills. The study, which used self-reflection surveys and pre-post assessments, revealed a discernible improvement in the speaking skills of the students after utilizing artificial intelligence tools [Dandu & Mohanacharyulu, 2023; 79-80]. Another research has been conducted on the function of social network-based interaction in AI-assisted language acquisition [Zou et al., 2023; 8-9]. Chinese university students participated in a study that discovered social networking platforms and interactive artificial intelligence speaking apps improved students' practice of speaking English. Speaking skills improved more in the experimental group (interactive activities) than in the control group (AI apps, no interaction). This demonstrates the possibility of improving language acquisition through the integration of artificial intelligence and social networking. Students' communication skills are demonstrated to be greatly improved when information and communication technology (ICT) and artificial intelligence (AI) tools are integrated into language education. Learners who were taught with ICT and artificial intelligence technologies did better than other students who were taught with traditional techniques, according to an experiment involving one hundred students, as stated by E.Madhavi et al. [Madhavi et al., 2023; 144]. In order to improve learning results, this study emphasizes how important it is to incorporate technology in teaching languages.

On top of that, the development of students' intercultural communicative competence can be greatly enhanced by artificial intelligence tools. Through the promotion of cultural competency, artificial intelligence, and mobile applications additionally assist in overcoming communication obstacles. The creation and completion of language activities with a cultural focus can be facilitated by artificial intelligence tools such as ChatGPT, as illustrated by a study on the application of AI in telecollaboration [McCallum, 2024; 156]. In addition to improving language proficiency, this method assists people gain a deeper comprehension of cultural peculiarities, which is vital for productive communication in today's interconnected world. Students can improve their communicative competence with the help of mobile applications, according to the next research carried out by Pavlo Tychyna in Uman State Pedagogical University. According to the study, mobile apps are reasonable and useful for utilization in the classroom since they promote group work, provide pertinent contexts for conversations, and necessitate minimal additional resources [Kumar, 2022; 138]. In order to build communicative competencies, mobile applications have become essential tools, claimed G.J. Robert [Robert, 2011; 3]. According to this author, interactive language learning applications such as Babbel and Memrise encourage speaking and writing practice in a fun and engaging way. To successfully reinforce skills in language, such applications incorporate interactive exercises and spaced repetition. By enabling group projects and conversations, and collaboration platforms like Microsoft Teams [Wea & Kuki, 2021; 2] and

Slack [White et al., 2017; 2], communication can be improved even more. Students can practice their interpersonal skills in a digital setting and collaborate with others on these platforms. Through the utilization of language exchange programs such as Tandem [Nushi & Khazaei, 2020; 242] and HelloTalk [Arsadah, 2024; 15], students can interact with native speakers and gain essential experience in real-world situations. By exposing students to a variety of cultural contexts, these interactions not only increase students' language proficiency but also their sociolinguistic competence.

In educational technology, gamification has become a major tactic, especially in language acquisition. As J.Hamari et al. [Hamari, 2014; 3026] stated, teachers can encourage students to practice their skills through challenges and incentives by adding game-like aspects to apps. Sustained practice and interest maintenance depend on this kind of involvement. Moreover, social connection is important for language learning according to J.P. Gee [Gee, 2004; 15]. As they stated, learners can interact with peers and exchange experiences through apps that offer forums or chat functions, which enhances the learning process. M.Byram [Byram, 1997; 7] argues that students' sociolinguistic comprehension, which is pivotal for effective communication, is improved through exposure to other cultures by these tools. Many educational applications additionally include accessibility features that guarantee language learning is inclusive of all students, including those with disabilities. Learners with different requirements can interact with language content more easily thanks to tools like text-to-speech and speech recognition [Al-Azawei et al., 2017; 57].

METHODS

This study employs a qualitative research methodology to analyze the impact of artificial intelligence and mobile applications on language acquisition. A literature review method was chosen as it allows for a comprehensive examination of existing studies, providing a broad understanding of how artificial intelligence and mobile apps enhance communicative competencies. This approach enables the synthesis of diverse perspectives and technologies, offering valuable insights into the specific tools and methods that foster improved language learning.

This research's qualitative approach makes it especially well-suited to capturing the complex ways that mobile applications and artificial intelligence (AI) affect communicative competence since they affect not just language proficiency but also the social and strategic aspects of communication. This study intends to identify patterns and links in language acquisition that might not be apparent through quantitative approaches alone by concentrating on the wide spectrum of AI-driven platforms.

A meta-analytic component has also been included to compare the results from several studies, guaranteeing that the conclusions derived from different artificial intelligence and mobile application tools provide a thorough understanding of their influence on language learning. This synthesis addresses potential differences in the efficacy of various technologies and contributes to the establishment of a stronger connection between language competency and AI-driven tools. By employing this technique, the study explores the pedagogical ramifications of integrating artificial intelligence into the instruction of second languages, going beyond superficial observations. This approach makes it possible to investigate in detail the ways in which certain artificial intelligence tools like language exchange platforms, chatbots, and gamified mobile applications affect the four aspects of communicative competence: discourse, grammatical, sociolinguistic, and strategic

skills. Furthermore, as AI-driven language learning tools are always changing, the adaptability of this research approach allows for future technical advancements. Because of the methodology's dynamic nature, the results reached can be adjusted to take into account new developments in the field.

Peer-reviewed publications, conference papers, and case studies from recognized journals were given priority in order to guarantee a thorough study. Studies that evaluated artificial intelligence technologies, mobile applications, or both in ESL learning contexts were the main emphasis of the inclusion criteria. Moreover, utilizing databases like Google Scholar, JSTOR, and Scopus, searches were carried out using keywords including “communicative competence”, “mobile apps in ESL & EFL education”, and “AI in language learning”. The methodological rigor and applicability of the studies to artificial intelligence and mobile application integration in language acquisition were then taken into consideration when classifying them. Finally, the analysis provides an in-depth understanding of the advantages and limitations of AI-assisted language acquisition by synthesizing data from various educational settings.

RESULTS

The analysis reveals several key findings:

1. **Personalization:** AI-driven systems adjust to students' development so that the material is always challenging and pertinent. Student motivation and engagement are raised by this flexibility. For instance, Duolingo adapts lessons according to user success using algorithms [Ghafar et al., 2023; 26]. Learners are more motivated and engaged when they receive this individualization. Students are free to work at their own pace, concentrating on their areas of weakness and moving through the stages as they gain proficiency in new skills. AI's capacity to continuously evaluate and adjust to student performance guarantees that learning paths are customized to meet the requirements of every student, resulting in a more focused and effective language curriculum development. ESL students, who frequently have distinct learning obstacles and diverse competence levels, need this level of customization the most.

2. **Instant Feedback:** Learning efficiency is greatly increased by tools that offer real-time adjustments, which assist students in instantly correcting their mistakes. Studies indicate that getting feedback immediately is essential for learning a language [Hattie & Timperley, 2007; 83]. Writing assignments can be corrected in real-time by using apps like Grammarly [Fitria, 2021; 66], which promotes better writing abilities. By providing instantaneous reinforcement, students can successfully learn from their mistakes and promote appropriate usage. In addition to encouraging self-regulated learning, real-time feedback allows learners to become more autonomous and in control of their language development. The ability to learn a language autonomously is essential for long-term success.

3. **Engagement with Gamification:** Mobile apps with gamified components create a fun and competitive learning environment that promotes regular practice. Students are kept engaged for extended periods by apps like Memrise and Babbel that incorporate leaderboards, incentives, and progress tracking. These features help promote healthy competition and a sense of accomplishment.

4. **Collaboration:** Peer-to-peer platforms foster cooperation and communication skills, which are necessary for proficient language use in everyday situations [Muck & Kluge, 2021; 305]. Numerous mobile applications facilitate cooperative projects, allowing students to interact and cooperate despite distance. Peer engagement is improved by real-time cooperation on

language assignments through the use of tools such as Google Docs [Ishtaiwa & Aburezeq, 2015; 86] and others. Through group projects and conversations facilitated by these platforms, students improve their communication skills in a nurturing setting. Collaborating with others enables students to enhance their pragmatic and sociolinguistic abilities, which are essential for creating conversational strategies and comprehending language that is appropriate for the given situation.

5. **Practical Experience:** Through tools that simulate real-world situations, learners can practice language in context. According to A.Parmaxi [Parmaxi, 2023; 173], virtual reality language learning platforms, for instance, provide students with immersive environments in which they can communicate in target languages. This real-world application assists with fluency and confidence building. Learners can close the gap between theory and application by interacting with native speakers or taking part in online discussions. By allowing students to interact with the language in a variety of real-life contexts—from casual conversations to business discussions—AI-driven simulations help students become more proficient communicators across a range of settings.

6. **Cultural Exposure:** Students' sociolinguistic awareness is improved when they have access to a variety of cultural scenarios via language exchange applications. These interactions help students become more proficient at negotiating language use in multicultural situations while also enhancing their linguistic abilities and intercultural competence. The importance of this cultural component is growing as students are prepared to use English in global settings.

In summary, learners' communication competencies improve as a result of the integration of AI and mobile applications in the language learning process.

DISCUSSION

There are advantages and disadvantages of integrating artificial intelligence and mobile applications in the language learning process. Teachers must take into account concerns like digital fairness and the possibility of over-reliance on technology even as these technologies improve communicative competencies [Selwyn, 2016; 121]. Inequalities in learning results may arise from the fact that certain students do not have equitable access to devices or reliable internet connections. In order to optimize the potential advantages of these tools teacher preparation programs should also place a strong emphasis on them for successful application. Teachers need to have the right tools to effectively incorporate technology into their lesson plans. Although artificial intelligence provides excellent opportunities for language practice, it cannot fully replace the social and emotional connections fostered by human interaction. Teachers, therefore, play an important role in integrating artificial intelligence tools into the classroom in a way that complements rather than replaces traditional methods. On the whole, maintaining a competitive edge in the ever-evolving technology landscape requires ongoing professional growth.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study highlights the transformative potential of artificial intelligence and mobile applications in enhancing students' communicative competence. By offering personalized, interactive, and real-time learning experiences, these technologies bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical language use. Since AI can adjust to the needs of the learner and provide immediate feedback, it is a valuable tool in language education, especially when it comes to developing critical communicative competencies. As these technologies advance, they will also become even more important in helping students master communicative strategies that are necessary for real-world communication. Despite this, it is important to recognize that

implementation of these powerful tools must be balanced, with AI and mobile apps serving as a complement to traditional teaching methods that involve human interaction and social learning rather than as a replacement for them. Teachers must be prepared to effectively integrate these technologies while ensuring students are not overly dependent on them; human communication involves subtle emotional and social aspects that technology cannot fully replicate.

Future research should continue to explore the long-term effects of these technologies, particularly in diverse learning environments, to maximize their potential for all students. Further research into how AI tools might be customized to accommodate various educational contexts, such as rural or under-resourced schools, and how to make them more inclusive particularly for students with disabilities would be helpful. In order to protect data security and privacy, more research should concentrate on the ethical implications of artificial intelligence in education.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

Several recommendations should be taken into consideration:

1. To improve language learning outcomes, educators should incorporate mobile apps and AI-driven technologies into their curricula.

2. Programs for professional development ought to be established to provide educators with the expertise they need to use these technologies efficiently.

3. Further research is needed concerning how artificial intelligence may be tailored to fit the unique requirements of various learner groups, including adult learners and students in multilingual settings. This will guarantee that artificial intelligence technologies are adaptable enough to meet the requirements and circumstances of diverse learning scenarios.

4. Emphasize inclusivity: that all students, especially those with impairments, can utilize instructional tools.

5. Finally, teachers should concentrate on creating a hybrid approach to language instruction that blends the advantages of face-to-face communication and collaborative learning environments with the capabilities of artificial intelligence and mobile apps.

By considering these recommendations, educators can develop a more successful and inclusive method of teaching languages that enables students to communicate effectively in a globalized society.

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